

Table S1. Locality information and environmental measures for eleven collection sites used to establish stock tanks in this study.

Species	Site ID	Collection Year	River	Elevation	pH	Temperature	Canopy Cover	Latitude	Longitude	Annual Rainfall
<i>P. prolifica</i>	OA	2014	Baluarte	40m	8-8.5	25°C	0%	N 23°3'45"	W 105°50'37.5"	481.4
	OB		Presidio	19m	7.5-8.0	25°C	5%	N 23°16'31.7"	W 106°14'27.5"	751.6
	OC		Piactla	45m	8-8.5	22°C	10%	N 23°53'17.1'	W 106°37'07.0"	751.6
	OD		Acaponeta	20m	7.5-8.0	23°C	0%	N 22°29'24.5"	W 105°21'19.4"	24
<i>P. infans</i>	IA	2014 & 2015	Ameca	1241m	8-8.5	25°C	25%	N 20°33'3.5"	W 103°57'7.5"	546.3
	IB		de la Pasión	1536m	8-8.5	22°C	25%	N 20°9'38.3"	W 103°2'20.0"	1076.4
	IC		Santiago	1191m	8-8.5	27°C	5%	N 21°12'26.4"	W 103°22'4.6"	805
	ID		Juchipala	1371m	9-9.5	20°C	0%	N 21°39'4.8"	W 102°57'56.0"	419.8
<i>P. gracilis</i>	GA	2004	Motagua	120m	N/A	N/A	N/A	N 14°57'51.5"	W 89°34'43.5"	1910.6
	GB	2014	Tampaón	101m	7-7.5	22°C	40%	N 21°58'33"	W 98°57'42"	1594
	GC		Coatzacoalcos	89.7m	8-8.5	21°C	12.5%	N 17°8'59"	W 95°7'6.1"	579

Table S2. Locality information and population statistics generated from do novo loci assembly of ddRAD sequencing data.

Species	Site ID	Collection Year	Total Sites Identified	Variant Sites	Loci Generated	Private Alleles	Observed Heterozygosity
<i>P. prolifica</i>	OA	2014	5,291,193	98,072	84,224	7,323	0.08
	OB		7,627,534	101,929		29,766	0.13
	OC		6,202,299	98,445		6,113	0.09
	OD		6,860,060	104,599		32,836	0.11
<i>P. infans</i>	IA	2014 & 2015	5,624,807	76,813	64,235	29,164	0.10
	IB		5,701,690	78,879		16,139	0.11
	IC		6,063,312	78,493		9,417	0.10
	ID		5,285,659	76,058		7,176	0.07
<i>P. gracilis</i>	GA	2004	3,737,089	54,041	49,126	12,065	0.09
	GB	2014	4,528,035	56,616		6,722	0.05
	GC		5,889,668	66,445		31,616	0.17

Table S3. Mean measure values estimated from intrapopulation crosses performed within this study and published data on late stage embryo mass (Frías-Alvarez, Macías Garcia et al. 2014) for each collection population.

Site ID	Mean Offspring Dry Mass (mg)	Mean Offspring Length (mm)	Mean Offspring Number	Days to First Birth	Reproductive Tissue Mass (mg)	Mean Published Mass of Late Stage Embryo (mg)
OA	0.85	8.8	52	43.7	31.5	N/A
OB	0.84	8.8	37	49.8	25.7	N/A
OC	0.77	9.0	41	44.2	47.0	N/A
OD	0.92	9.1	36.7	46.3	37.1	N/A
IA	1.61	9.0	36.5	45.5	63.5	1.0
IB	1.60	8.8	40.7	42.3	42.8	0.8
IC	1.75	9.3	34.7	50.3	50.8	1.0
ID	1.62	9.6	35.7	41.3	73.3	0.8
GA	1.79	10.1	13.8	40.3	31.0	N/A
GB	1.79	10.6	11	68.7	32.4	1.3
GC	1.72	10.7	14.8	41.8	32.4	1.1

Table S4. Overall species means estimated for every measure collected from the crosses performed in this study.

	Offspring Dry Mass (mg)	Maternal Wet Mass (mg)	Offspring Total Length (mm)	Offspring Number	Days to First Birth	Viable Embryos	Inviabile Embryos	Reproductive Allocation (%)
<i>P. gracilis</i>	1.76	0.39	10.4	13.4	45.4	5.7	0.1	7.97
<i>P. infans</i>	1.54	0.54	9.12	35.4	39.5	13.3	0	11.31
<i>P. prolifica</i>	0.67	0.48	8.07	39.4	43.3	18.6	0.2	4.28

Figure S1. Multidimensional scaling plot of environmental measures recorded at the eleven collection sites used to establish stock tanks in this study.

Figure S2. Difference in observed and expected embryo length (top) and mass (bottom) of offspring resulting from intrapopulation (green) and interpopulation (tan) crosses performed in the placental species *Poecilopsis prolifica* modeled as a function of the mass of their mother. The shaded region represents the 95% confidence interval.